

Oxidation of L-tyrosine by sodium *N*-bromobenzenesulfonamide in alkaline medium : a kinetic and mechanistic study

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The kinetics of oxidation of L-tyrosine (Tyr) by sodium *N*-bromobenzenesulfonamide or bromamine-B (BAB) has been studied in NaOH medium at 283 K. The rates are first order in both $[BAB]_0$ and $[Tyr]_0$ and inverse fractional order in $[OH^-]$. Ionic strength and halide ion variations or the presence of added reaction product, benzenesulfonamide, has no pronounced effect on the rate. The dielectric effect is positive. The reaction has been studied at different temperatures and activation parameters for the composite reaction are computed. Solvent isotope effect is also studied. The thermodynamic parameters for the equilibrium step and activation parameters for the rate determining step are evaluated. A plausible mechanism consistent with the observed kinetics is proposed.

The chemistry of aromatic sulphonyl haloamines has evoked considerable interest, as they are sources of halonium cations, hypohalite species, and *N*-anions which act both as bases and nucleophiles. The prominent members of this group are chloramine-T and chloramine-B and the mechanistic aspects of many of these reactions have been documented¹. Bromamine-B (BAB; $C_6H_5SO_2NBrNa \cdot 1.5H_2O$) is gaining importance as a mild oxidant² and is found to be a better oxidizing agent than the chloro compound.

The oxidation of amino acids is of utmost importance, both from a purely chemical point of view and from the point of view of its bearing on the mechanism of amino acid metabolism. L-Tyrosine (Tyr) is an aromatic amino acid and it serves important functions in our biological systems and plays a significant role in metabolism. Tyrosine finds extensive applications in pharmaceuticals³. A review of literature shows that amino acids have been oxidized by a large number of oxidants but there is limited information on the oxidation kinetics of L-tyrosine. As a part of our broad program on the mechanistic studies of amino acids with organic haloamines, we report, herein the kinetics of oxidation of L-tyrosine by BAB at 283 K in alkaline medium in the present communication.

Results and discussion

The kinetics of oxidation of L-tyrosine by BAB was

investigated at several initial concentrations of the reactants in NaOH medium at 283 K.

With the substrate in excess, at constant $[NaOH]$, $[Tyr]_0$ and temperature, plots of $\log [BAB]$ vs time were linear ($r > 0.9928$) indicating a first order dependence on $[BAB]_0$. Values of pseudo-first order rate constants (k) are unaltered with variation of $[BAB]_0$ (Table 1) confirming first order dependence on $[BAB]_0$. The rate increased with increase in $[Tyr]_0$ (Table 1) and a plot of $\log k$ vs $\log [Tyr]$ was linear ($r = 0.9998$) with a slope of unity indicating a first order dependence on $[Tyr]_0$. Further, plot of k vs $[Tyr]$ gave a straight line ($r = 0.9996$) passing through the origin indicating that the oxidant-substrate complex has transient existence. The rate decreased with increase in $[NaOH]$ (Table 1). A plot of $\log k$ vs $\log [NaOH]$ was linear ($r = 0.9995$) with a slope of -0.63 , indicating a fractional inverse dependence of rate on hydroxide ion concentration.

Addition of the reaction product, benzenesulfonamide and halide ions in the form of NaCl or NaBr (2.0×10^{-4} – 2.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³) or variation of ionic strength of the medium (0.1 – 0.8 mol dm⁻³) had no pronounced effect on the rate. The effect of dielectric constant (D) of the solvent medium of the reaction mixture was studied by varying the percentage of methanol (0–40%, v/v). The rate increased with increase in methanol content. A plot of $\log k$ vs $1/D$ gave a straight line ($r = 0.9992$) with a

Table 1. Effect of varying concentrations of oxidant, substrate and acid on the rate of reaction

$I = 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; temp. = 283 K

$10^4 [\text{BAB}]_0$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^3 [\text{Tyr}]_0$ mol dm ⁻³	10 [NaOH] mol dm ⁻³	$10^4 k$ s ⁻¹
2.0	4.0	1.0	7.15
4.0	4.0	1.0	7.04
6.0	4.0	1.0	7.10
8.0	4.0	1.0	7.00
10.0	4.0	1.0	7.18
4.0	2.0	1.0	3.60
4.0	4.0	1.0	7.04
4.0	8.0	1.0	14.1
4.0	12.0	1.0	20.1
4.0	18.0	1.0	29.8
4.0	4.0	0.5	11.2
4.0	4.0	1.0	7.04
4.0	4.0	2.0	4.50
4.0	4.0	4.0	3.05
4.0	4.0	6.0	2.30

positive slope. Blank experiments indicated that methanol was slightly oxidized (< 2%) by BAB under the present experimental conditions. This was taken into account in the calculation of net reaction rate constant for the oxidation of tyrosine each time.

The reaction was studied at different temperatures (283–298 K), keeping other experimental conditions constant. From the linear Arrhenius plot of $\log k$ vs $1/T$ ($r = 0.9871$), values of activation parameters, energy of activation (E_a), enthalpy of activation (ΔH^\ddagger), free energy of activation (ΔG^\ddagger) and entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) for the composite reaction were calculated as 74.3, 71.9, 86.9 kJ mol⁻¹ and $-51.9 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively. The solvent isotope effect was studied in D₂O. The reaction was further retarded with $k = 6.12 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ in D₂O medium and $7.04 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ in H₂O, leading to a solvent isotope effect, $k(\text{H}_2\text{O})/k(\text{D}_2\text{O}) = 1.15$. The reaction mixture failed to initiate polymerization of aqueous acrylamide solution, indicating the absence of free radicals.

Amino acids are known to exist as neutral molecules (S), zwitter ions (S^o), anions (S⁻) and cations (SH⁺) in aqueous solutions and dissociation dependence upon the pH of the medium :

Since the organic haloamines have similar chemical properties, it is expected that similar equilibria exist in solutions of these compounds⁴. In general, BAB undergoes a two-electron change in its reactions. The oxidation potential of BAB-PhSO₂NH₂ is pH dependent and decreases with increase in pH of the medium (1.14 V at pH 0.65 and 0.50 V at pH 12.0). The possible oxidizing species^{4–6} in acidified BAB solutions are the conjugate acid PhSO₂NHBr, the dibromamine PhSO₂NBr₂ and HOBr. In alkaline solutions of BAB, PhSO₂NBr₂ does not exist and the possible species are the anion PhSO₂NBr⁻ and OBr⁻ which would be transformed into more reactive oxidizing species PhSO₂NHBr and HOBr in the course of the reaction in alkaline medium. Several researchers^{5,7} have observed the retarding influence of OH⁻ ions on the rate of BAB reactions with a number of substrates and suggested that the reaction of weakly alkaline solutions of BAB is due to the formation of the conjugate acid PhSO₂NHBr from PhSO₂NBr⁻ in a OH⁻ retarding step. In view of these points, Scheme 1 can be proposed for the oxidation of tyrosine by BAB in alkaline medium to account the experimental results :

Scheme 1

In Scheme 1, X represents the complex intermediate species whose structure is shown in Scheme 2 where a plausible mechanistic interpretation of L-tyrosine oxidation by BAB in alkaline medium is proposed.

If [BAB]_t represents the total effective concentration of BAB, and assuming

$$[\text{BAB}]_t = [\text{PhSO}_2\text{NBr}^-] + [\text{PhSO}_2\text{NHBr}]$$

rate law (2) can be derived :

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{-d[\text{BAB}]}{dt} = \frac{K_1 k_2 [\text{BAB}]_t [\text{Tyr}] [\text{H}_2\text{O}]}{[\text{OH}^-] + K_1 [\text{H}_2\text{O}]} \quad (2)$$

Rate law (2) is in agreement with the experimental results.

Since rate = k [BAB]₁, eqn. (2) can be transformed into eqns. (3) and (4),

$$\frac{1}{k} = \frac{[\text{OH}^-] + K_1[\text{H}_2\text{O}]}{K_1 k_2 [\text{Tyr}] [\text{H}_2\text{O}]} \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{1}{k} = \frac{[\text{OH}^-]}{K_1 k_2 [\text{Tyr}] [\text{H}_2\text{O}]} + \frac{1}{k_2 [\text{Tyr}]} \quad (4)$$

Scheme 2

Plot of $1/k$ vs $1/[\text{Tyr}]$ was linear ($r = 0.9991$) and which passes through the origin confirming observed kinetics. Further, from the slope and intercept of the linear plot of $1/k$ vs $[\text{OH}^-]$, values of hydrolysis constant of BAB (K_1) and decomposition constant of oxidant-substrate complex (k_2) were found to be 2.14×10^{-3} and $0.31 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively at 283 K. The thermodynamic parameters for the equilibrium step and activation parameters for the rate determining step were evaluated as follows : Hydroxyl ion concentration (as in Table 1) was varied at several temperatures (283, 288, 293 and 298 K) and values of K_1 and k_2 were determined at each temperature using eqn. (4). A Van't Hoff plot was made for the variation of K_1 with temperature (i.e., $\log K_1$ vs $1/T$; $r = 0.9857$) and values of thermodynamic parameters for the equilibrium step, ΔH , ΔS and ΔG were calculated. Arrhenius plot of $\log k_2$ vs $1/T$ ($r = 0.9900$) yielded the activation parameters for the rate determining step of Scheme 1. These values are presented in Table 2. A comparison with the activation parameters obtained for the overall reaction shows that the values mainly refers to the rate determining step supporting the fact that reaction before the rate

Table 2. Values of K_1 and k_2 at different temperatures and thermodynamic and activation parameters for equilibrium and rate determining steps

$[\text{BAB}]_0 = 4.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{Tyr}]_0 = 4.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $I = 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

Temperature (K)	$10^3 K_1$	k_2 $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$
283	2.14	0.31
288	2.30	0.42
293	2.49	0.83
298	2.95	1.25

Activation parameters	Parameter	Value
	E_a kJ mol^{-1}	63.8
	ΔH (ΔH^\ddagger) kJ mol^{-1}	14.0 (61.4)
	ΔG (ΔG^\ddagger) kJ mol^{-1}	11.6 (72.3)
	ΔS (ΔS^\ddagger) $\text{J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$	8.4 (-37.7)

determining step is fast, involving little activation energy. The proposed Scheme 1 is supported by the following experimental observation.

For a reaction involving a fast pre-equilibrium H^+ or OH^- ion transfer, the rate increases in D_2O medium since D_3O^+ and OD^- are a stronger acid and a stronger base, respectively, than H_3O^+ and OH^- ions⁸. The reverse holds for reaction involving retardation by H^+ or OH^- ions. Hence, the proposed mechanism is also supported by the decrease in rate in D_2O medium. The magnitude, however, is small [$k(H_2O)/k(D_2O) = 1.15$] compared to the expected value of 2 to 3 times greater, which can be attributed to the fractional order dependence on $[OH^-]$.

The effect of varying solvent composition and dielectric constant (D) on the rate has been described in several studies⁹. For a limiting case of zero angle approach between the two dipoles or an anion-dipole system, Amis¹⁰ has shown that a plot of $\log k$ vs $1/D$ gives a straight line. It gives a negative slope for a reaction between an anion and a dipole or between two dipoles and a positive slope for a reaction between a cation and a dipole. The positive dielectric effect, in the present studies, supports the involvement of ion-dipole interaction in the rate determining step.

The proposed mechanism is also supported by the moderate values of energy of activation. The fairly high positive value of free energy of activation and enthalpy of activation indicate that the transition state is highly solvated, while the negative entropy of activation reflects the formation of a compact and a more ordered transition state. Addition of halide ions had no effect on the rate indicating that no interhalogen or free bromine was formed. The reaction product benzenesulfonamide does not influence the rate, showing that it is not involved in a pre-equilibrium. Variation of ionic strength of the medium does not alter the rate indicating that non-ionic species are involved in the rate determining step. All these observations are also in conformity with the proposed mechanism.

Experimental

Bromamine-B was prepared by the reported procedure¹¹. The purity of BAB was checked iodometrically through its active bromine content and the compound was further characterized by its ^{13}C FT-NMR spectrum (obtained on a Bruker WH 270-MHz nuclear magnetic resonance spectrometer) with D_2O as solvent and TMS as the internal standard (ppm relative to TMS) 143.38 (C-1, carbon attached to S atom), 134.30 (C-4, para to the hetero atom), 131.26 (C-2,6), 129.31 (C-3,5). An

aqueous solution of BAB was standardized iodometrically and preserved in brown bottles to prevent its photochemical deterioration. L-Tyrosine (Merck) was used as such and the solution was prepared in 0.01 mol dm^{-3} NaOH. The alkali present in the substrate solution is also taken into account in the calculation of the total alkali present in each case. All other chemicals were of AnalaR grade. The ionic strength of the medium was maintained at a high constant value ($I = 0.50 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) using a concentrated solution of sodium perchlorate. Solvent isotope studies were made with D_2O (99.4% isotopic purity) supplied by the Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Mumbai, India. Permittivity of the reaction medium was changed by the addition of methanol in varying proportions (v/v) and the values of permittivity of methanol-water mixtures reported in the literature¹² were employed. Triply distilled water was used throughout.

Kinetic measurements : Kinetic runs were performed under pseudo-first order conditions with excess of the substrate over the oxidant at 283 K. Reactions were carried out in glass stoppered pyrex boiling tubes coated black on the outside to eliminate photochemical effects. The oxidant and the requisite amounts of Tyr, NaOH, and $NaClO_4$ solutions and water (for constant total volume) taken in separate boiling tubes were thermostated for 30 min at 283 K. The reaction was initiated by the rapid addition of a measured amount of BAB to the mixture and was shaken intermittently for uniform concentration. The progress of the reaction was monitored by withdrawing known aliquots at regular time intervals and determining the amount of unreacted BAB iodometrically. The course of reaction was studied upto 80–85% conversion. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k) calculated from the linear plots of $\log [\text{oxidant}]$ vs time were reproducible to within $\pm 4\%$. Regression analysis of the experimental data was carried out on an EC-75 statistical calculator to obtain the regression coefficient, r .

Stoichiometry and product analysis : Varying ratios of oxidant to substrate ($[BAB] \gg [Tyr]$) in the presence of 0.10 mol dm^{-3} NaOH were equilibrated at 283 K for 48 h. The determination of the unconsumed BAB in the reaction mixture showed that one mole of Tyr consumed three moles of BAB :

The reduction product of BAB, benzenesulfonamide ($PhSO_2NH_2$) was recrystallized from dichloromethane/

petroleum ether (m.p. = 149–150°, lit. m.p. = 150–152°). An R_f value of 0.36 was determined from TLC¹³ using (CH₂Cl₂ + CHCl₃, 7 : 3, v/v) as the solvent system and iodine as the spray reagent. The reported R_f value is consistent with the literature value¹³. The oxidation product of L-tyrosine was found to be 2-(3,5-dibromo-4-hydroxyphenyl)acetaldehyde. It was detected by elementary analysis, Beilsteins test and functional groups were identified by usual tests. The aldehyde was confirmed by its 2,4-DNP derivative¹⁴. The presence of 2-(3,5-dibromo-4-hydroxyphenyl)acetaldehyde was further confirmed by ¹H NMR and mass spectral analyses. ¹H NMR spectrum in CDCl₃ has been recorded on a Bruker AMX-400 MHz spectrometer using tetramethylsilane as an internal standard. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 3.61, (2H, d, *J* 1.8 Hz, CH₂); 5.87 (1H, s, OH), 7.31 (2H, s, ArH), 9.72, (1H, t, *J* 1.8 Hz, CHO).

Mass spectrum : The GC-MS data were obtained on a 17A Shimadzu gas chromatograph with a QP-5050 Shimadzu mass spectrometer using the electron impact ionization technique. The mass spectrum shows a molecular ion peak at 294, clearly confirming 2-(3,5-dibromo-4-hydroxyphenyl)acetaldehyde. Other peaks observed can be interpreted in accordance with the observed structure.

Ammonia was quantitatively estimated by the microkjeldahl procedure, while CO₂ was identified by the conventional lime water test.

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